

Digital Influences and conceptions of masculinity: Rethinking wellbeing through a lens of interpersonal recognition

Introduction

This brief offers an alternative perspective on digital wellbeing recommendations that draw on risk management approaches to ensure the safety of young people. These strategies often take the form of advice to cancel, report, and block users, or to step away from the platform after toxic online encounters. While such measures may provide immediate relief for the targeted individual, they do little to address the underlying issue: the quality of interactions in online environments. They also do not equip those affected with the resilience needed to cope with the potential moral injuries that can arise from these experiences, nor do they provide language to understand and contextualise the perpetrator's actions.

Through a conception of intersubjective recognition (i.e. social validation[1]), we aim to reframe wellbeing as a reflexive, interpersonal experience. This approach offers an empowering vocabulary for understanding the impact of negative digital experiences, while also helping individuals intentionally seek out and cultivate positive ones as a way of taking charge of their wellbeing.

Why is intersubjective recognition key to digital wellbeing?

Online, (young) people often encounter digital environments that simultaneously enable growth (connection, learning, income, identity play) and amplify harm (misogyny, echo chambers, performance pressure, etc.).

Traditional interventions

Traditional interventions either over rely on safety messaging, the dos and don't of online engagement, which can come across as paternalistic, or on skills training, which largely ignores the contextual, structural, and power dimensions of such interactions.

The idea of recognition, which we will convey here through a perspective of “social validation”, i.e., the understanding that our social existence is to a great part contingent on the judgement others make of us, offers an explanatory basis for understanding the impact of digital experiences on one’s self conception, i.e., how we see ourselves in relation to others. This, in turn, is reflected in how we develop our sense of wellbeing.

Following this perspective, digital wellbeing depends on whether people consistently experience care/love, rights, and social esteem in their everyday online interactions and across the social spheres that shape our social existence. When social validation is absent or withdrawn - be it through shaming, opaque norms and rules, or status determined by arbitrary metrics - both wellbeing and meaningful participation are undermined. Conversely, when social validation is present, i.e., when the individual feels cared for, has their rights respected and is treated fairly, and receives support from the wider community, they are more likely to develop self-confidence, self-respect, and self-esteem. These forms of self-conception are the psychological bedrock of healthy participation and contribute to a more balanced and harmonious social existence

Social validation

[1] is used here as a lay translation of Axel Honneth’s concept of recognition, which describes the ways individuals form a positive relation to self through experiencing respect, esteem, and care from others.

The link between social validation and wellbeing

Digital environments can produce “double-edged” experiences, in that they can both enable support and harm. Institutional responses, be it through policies, safeguarding guidelines or punitive measures, tend to rely on sanctions or the provision of information. Yet, these approaches rarely provide alternatives to the sense of belonging, fairness, or social support that young people seek when they go online to find community or connection.

Self-realisation

Self-realisation and meaningful social participation in online environments are contingent on social validation across three spheres of engagement:

1. In a private sphere of family, friends, and intimate relationships, individuals expect to both give and receive care: an affective form of support that fosters self-confidence by reassuring us that there are people in our close circle who genuinely care for us. Harmony is disturbed when uncaring actions take place.
2. In the public sphere that operates on the principles of moral and legal rights, there is an understanding that individuals have rights and duties: individuals are understood to hold both rights and duties: rights that protect them, and duties that require them to respect the rights of others. When people see themselves as right bearers, they can develop self-respect because, knowing that their autonomy and dignity do not depend on others' personal opinions. This harmony is disrupted when rights are not mutually respected, or become one sided.
3. In the sphere of wider community engagement, individuals are seen as community member who value one another for the unique qualities, skills, and contributions each person brings to shared social life. There is an expectation that individuals can co-exist, supported by a common understanding of how to participate respectfully in community life. Harmony is disrupted when individuals are denied basic esteem, for example, when they are subjected to gratuitous hostility which signals that their contributions or identities are not valued within the community.

Sphere of social validation/ interpersonal recognition	Core expectations	Self-concept impacted	Positive and negative implications
Care	Receiving and giving emotional support, and trust within close relationships (family, friends, intimate ties)	Self-confidence: a sense of being genuinely valued and cared for by those in one's inner circle	+ Meaningful digital interactions can strengthen emotional bonds - Lack of care online (ghosting, exclusion, aggressive communication, etc.) can undermine confidence
Rights	Being recognised as a rights bearing individual with entitlements and duties; expectations of fair treatment and respect	Self-respect: respecting one's dignity and autonomy independently of others' opinions/actions	+ Respectful interactions, observation of ethical conduct and fair treatment - Rights violations (harassment, doxxing, humiliation and abuse) erode trust and participation
Esteem	Collective support for one's contributions, skills, and unique qualities, even from strangers or wider community	Self-esteem: feeling valued for what one is and brings to collective experience	+ Opportunities for valued contribution foster a sense of worth. - Toxic comments, gratuitous hostility undermine social esteem

Table 1 - Three spheres of social validation/intersubjective recognition and their relevance to digital engagement

Social validation, as a form of feeling respected, is a human need

Through a lens of social validation, digital wellbeing grows when these spheres of recognition are sustained through everyday practices that cultivate healthy, mutual relationships with others. Social validation, in the true sense, cannot be claimed or enforced; it must be given freely, and, as a form of respect, depends fundamentally on reciprocity.

Digital forms of social validation, such as likes, number of followers and reshares, offer a superficial sense of wellbeing. Their effects are ephemeral, prompting individuals to seek repeated exposure to screens in pursuit of that momentary “feel good”; an impression that lacks depth and lasting meaning.

This understanding of social validation calls for more explicit efforts to articulate shared ethical norms associated with online communication and interaction, clarifying both the expectations placed on participants and the impacts these interactions can have on one’s sense of self.

The need for social validation as a form of promoting healthy and ethical forms of digital engagement has an impact on our affective development, i.e., our emotional understanding of who we are and how we are regarded by others. Yet meaningful participation online also requires rational discourse: ways of communicating anchored in deliberation as a way to acknowledge the perspectives, claims, and intentions of others.

From an ethical standpoint, individuals seeking to give and receive genuine social validation must mutually recognise one another as free and equal agents. This mutual recognition is essential for reciprocity.

Power imbalance

When relationships become asymmetric, through power imbalances, exploitative content, coercion, or dismissive behaviour, the conditions for mutuality and authenticity are disrupted, weakening the potential for meaningful social validation and healthy digital engagement.

It is therefore important for individuals to learn how to distinguish the quality of the interactions they experience online, recognising when exchanges are genuinely reciprocal and when they are merely parasocial. This awareness can help them assess how these interactions affect their sense of self, including whether they enhance or diminish their wellbeing. With this understanding, individuals can make informed choices about when to remain in a digital environment and when to step away.

When experiences fail to offer social validation, the benefits of engagement disappear, signalling the need to seek out healthier, more supportive environments. The ultimate goal is respect.

Costa, C. (2026). Digital Influences and conceptions of masculinity: Rethinking wellbeing through an alternative conceptual tool (pp.1-7). NorthFutures.